

Interconversions of Anilides from Malonic Ester

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The reaction of malonic ester with anilines affording mono- and dianilides has been studied by a number of workers^{1,2,3,4}. Recently, George and Ittyerah have studied the formation of carboxyaceto *o*-, *m*- and *p*-chloroanilides by hydrolysing *in situ* the corresponding carbethoxy derivatives formed, following the removal of the relatively insoluble dianilides⁵. Our interest in the preferential formation of monoanilides arose from their utility as intermediates in the recent synthesis of several quinoline derivatives, e.g., Camoquin, a well established drug^{6,7}.

Diethyl malonate reacts readily with *p*-anisidine affording a mixture of carbethoxy aceto-*p*-anisidide (I) and malon-*p*-dianisidide (II)⁶. At 170° using 4 molar equivalents of diethylmalonate, *p*-anisidine gave monoanisidide (I) and dianisidide (II) in a molar ratio of 7 : 1. Slow addition of *p*-anisidine to diethyl malonate, however raised the monoanisidide (I) to dianisidide (II) ratio to 10.3 : 1⁷. At this point it was considered to be of interest to study whether the anilides are experimentally interconvertible.

Monoanisidide (I) and dianisidide (II) were obtained in the molar ratio of nearly 1.30 : 1 when equimolecular amounts of *p*-anisidine and diethyl malonate were used. An equimolecular mixture of dianisidide (II) and diethyl malonate when allowed to equilibrate for 6 hr. at 170°, gave the monoanisidide (I) to dianisidide (II) in the same molar ratio. It is at 170° the heterogeneous reactants transformed into a homogeneous melt and accordingly the reactions were carried out at this temperature. Monoanisidide (I) when kept at 170° gave the monoanisidide (I) and the dianisidide (II) also in the same molar ratio. On the other hand the monoanisidide (I) on heating at 170°/10 mm, allowing the malonic ester formed to distil off, was quantitatively converted to the dianisidide (II).

1. M. Freund, *Berich. Chem*, 1884, **17**, 133.
2. L. Rugheimer and R. Hoffmann, *ibid.*, 1885, **18**, 2978.
3. M. A. Whitley, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, **83**, 24.
4. F. D. Chattaway and F. A. Mason, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **20**, 2059.
5. M. V. George and P. I. Ittyerah, *Agra University Journal of Research*, 1955, **IV**, 299.
6. A. K. Sen and U. P. Basu, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1957, **34**, 906.
7. A. K. Sen and K. Mitra, *ibid.*, 1965, **42**, 852.

Similar studies with *m*-chloroaniline gave the monoanilide to dianilide in the molar ratio of 1.45 : 1.

The interconversion of mono and dianilides from malonic ester thus appear to be an experimentally reversible reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

The melting points and mixed melting points of the compounds were found to be identical with samples prepared according to published procedures. The overall yield of the mixed anilides, in all cases, accounts for over 90% of the anilines present.

Carbethoxyaceto p-anisidide (I) and malon-di-p-anisidide (II) :

(a) A mixture of *p*-anisidine (6.15 g., 0.05 mole) and diethyl malonate (8.0 g., 0.05 mole) was heated during 1 hr. to 170° and kept at that temperature for 6 hr. The mixture was cooled, triturated with petroleum ether (80–100°) (25 ml) and filtered. The dried mass was warmed with ethanol (75 ml). After cooling, malon-di-*p*-anisidide was collected (4.65 g., 0.0148 mole) m.p. 226–228°. The filtrate was concentrated and made turbid with water. On cooling carbethoxy aceto *p*-anisidide crystallised out (4.55 g., 0.0192 mole), m.p. 69.70°.

(b) A mixture of malon di-*p*-anisidide (7.85 g., 0.025 mole) (II) and diethyl malonate (4.0 g., 0.025 mole) was heated under reflux to 170° when the heterogeneous mixture transformed into a homogeneous melt and kept at that temperature for 6 hr. Malon di-*p*-anisidide (II) (4.55 g., 0.0145 mole) and carbethoxyaceto *p*-anisidide (I) (4.50 g., 0.0190 mole) were isolated as described in (a).

(c) Carbethoxyaceto *p*-anisidide (I) (11.85 g., 0.05 mole) was heated under reflux at 170° for 2 hr. and worked up as described under (a), affording malon di-*p*-anisidide (4.2 g., 0.0132 mole) and carbethoxyaceto *p*-anisidide (4.03 g., 0.017 mole).

(d) Carbethoxyaceto *p*-anisidide (1.185 g., 0.005 mole) (I) was set for distillation at 170°/10 mm. After 2 hr. the residual product obtained was found to be malon di-*p*-anisidide, yield 95%.

Carbethoxyaceto m-chloroanilide and m,m-dichloro malondianilide :—

(a) A mixture of *m*-chloroaniline (12.7 g., 0.1 mole) and diethyl malonate (16 g., 0.1 mole) was kept at 170° for 4 hr. the evolved ethanol being allowed to distil out. The cooled mixture was triturated with petroleum ether (80–100°) (3 × 15 ml), digested with hot benzene (100 ml) and cooled. The separated *m,m*-dichloro malon-dianilide (8.8 g., 0.0272 mole) melted at 173°

On removal of benzene from the mother liquor left the carbethoxyaceto-*m*-chloroanilide as an oil (9.7 g., 0.04 mole, based on its conversion to dianilide, see below) which could not be induced to crystallise. Attempted distillation under reduced pressure transformed it into *m,m*-dichloro malondianilide and diethyl malonate.

(b) The crude carbethoxyaceto *m*-chloroanilide, as obtained above (a), was heated with *m*-chloroaniline (7.0 g., 0.0549 mole) at 160°, ethanol formed being allowed to escape. The residue was digested with hot benzene (100 ml) and cooled. The separated *m-m*-dichloro malondianilide weighed 12.8 g., (0.04 mole).

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